

Artificial Intelligence Algorithms for Designing Synthetic Biological Systems and Predicting Their Behavior.

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a pivotal tool in advancing synthetic biology, revolutionizing the design and prediction of intricate biological systems with unprecedented precision. Synthetic biology aims to engineer biological entities or reconfigure existing systems for a spectrum of applications spanning medicine, environmental sustainability, and industrial biotechnology. The integration of AI algorithms, encompassing machine learning, neural networks, and evolutionary strategies, addresses fundamental challenges posed by biological complexity and variability. By harnessing vast datasets and computational models, AI-driven predictive tools empower researchers to efficiently design genetic circuits, optimize metabolic pathways, and engineer organisms tailored to specific functionalities. These advancements enable anticipatory modeling of system behaviours under diverse environmental conditions, enhancing reliability and efficacy in synthetic biology applications.

This paper delves into the transformative impact of AI in synthetic biology through a series of illustrative case studies. These examples demonstrate how AI facilitates the creation of sophisticated biological constructs, such as dynamic genetic circuits capable of logic operations and biosensing, and optimized metabolic pathways for enhanced production of biofuels and pharmaceuticals. Moreover, AI-driven predictive analytics enable the simulation of complex biological interactions and the prediction of outcomes, thereby guiding experimental design and accelerating innovation cycles.

The interdisciplinary synergy between AI and synthetic biology promises to unlock novel opportunities for addressing global challenges and revolutionizing biological engineering.

1.0 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become an indispensable tool in various scientific disciplines, and its integration into synthetic biology is revolutionizing the field. .

Synthetic biology involves designing and constructing new biological entities or redesigning existing biological systems for useful purposes, such as medical therapies, environmental sustainability, and industrial applications. The complexity and variability inherent in biological systems present significant challenges in design and prediction. AI algorithms offer powerful solutions by leveraging vast amounts of biological data, sophisticated computational models, and advanced machine learning techniques. .

AI in synthetic biology can be broadly categorized into two primary functions: designing synthetic biological systems and predicting their behavior. . The design aspect involves creating novel biological constructs, such as genetic circuits, metabolic pathways, and engineered organisms, using AI-driven tools to optimize for desired characteristics. These tools can automate the design process, reduce time and cost, and enhance the precision and efficiency of synthetic biology projects. .

The predictive aspect focuses on understanding and forecasting the behavior of these engineered systems within biological environments. Predictive models help anticipate how synthetic constructs will function under various conditions, their interactions with native biological systems, and potential emergent behaviours. This is crucial for ensuring the safety, reliability, and effectiveness of synthetic biological applications. .

Significant milestones in synthetic biology include the development of genetic circuits capable of performing sophisticated functions such as logic operations, oscillations, and biosensing. These achievements underscore the potential of synthetic biology to engineer biological systems with tailored functionalities, supported by robust mathematical models that ensure reliability and efficiency in design. .

Despite these advancements, challenges persist in achieving robust predictability across diverse biological contexts and environmental conditions. Variability in genetic expression, metabolic activity, and cellular environments complicates the accurate prediction of synthetic biological system behaviours. Current approaches often rely on iterative experimental testing and refinement, highlighting the need for advanced computational tools and methodologies. .

This research paper focuses on addressing these challenges through the application of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms in the design of synthetic biological systems. AI techniques offer novel opportunities to enhance the predictability, efficiency, and complexity of biological circuit design. . By leveraging AI-driven approaches, researchers aim to optimize the design process, improve the accuracy of predictive models, and accelerate the development of innovative synthetic biology applications. .

The paper will as well explore current methodologies and advancements in AI-driven design of synthetic biological systems, showcasing case studies where AI has successfully been applied. It will seek to discuss the potential of AI to revolutionize synthetic biology by enabling the design of robust and adaptive biological systems for applications in biomedicine, environmental remediation, and industrial biotechnology. Through interdisciplinary collaboration between AI researchers and synthetic biologists, this paper aims to chart new frontiers in the design and engineering of synthetic biological systems with unprecedented functionalities and reliability. .

2.0 Literature Review

Synthetic biology integrates principles from biology, engineering, and computer science to innovate and manipulate biological systems. . At its core, it aims to create novel biological components, devices, and systems that do not exist in nature, or to modify existing biological entities for specific applications. This interdisciplinary approach enables scientists to design genetic circuits and metabolic pathways that perform desired functions, such as producing pharmaceuticals or biofuels. It involves constructing artificial biological parts and systems, or tweaking natural biological processes, to achieve goals that range from improving healthcare to enhancing industrial processes. .

The field also addresses challenges such as predicting and controlling the behavior of these engineered biological systems, standardizing genetic parts for reliability, and navigating ethical considerations in biotechnology advancements. . Central to the practice of synthetic biology are methodologies such as genetic engineering, metabolic engineering, and the use of CRISPR/Cas systems. These methodologies provide the tools and frameworks necessary to advance our understanding and capabilities in biotechnology. .

Genetic Circuits

At the core of synthetic biology are genetic circuits, which are akin to electronic circuits but operate within living cells. Genetic circuits are networks of genes and regulatory elements designed to perform specific functions, such as processing inputs, executing logic operations, or producing outputs in a controlled manner. . These circuits are constructed using genetic components such as promoters, genes, and terminators, carefully arranged to control gene expression and cellular behaviour. .

A genetic circuit might be designed to detect the presence of a particular chemical in the environment and, in response, trigger the production of a therapeutic protein. This precise control over gene expression allows synthetic biologists to program cells to perform complex tasks. Applications of genetic circuits are vast, ranging from medical diagnostics and treatment to environmental monitoring and bio-manufacturing. . By enabling cells to respond to specific stimuli in predetermined ways, genetic circuits pave the way for innovative solutions to numerous biological and medical challenges. .

For instance, a genetic circuit developed by Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) researchers uses a combination of genetic parts to create a bacterial cell that can detect and respond to environmental arsenic. This engineered bacterium contains a genetic circuit that activates the production of a detectable signal, such as a fluorescent protein, when arsenic is present in the environment. This application highlights the potential of genetic circuits to create biosensors that can monitor environmental pollutants and provide early warnings of contamination. .

Metabolic Engineering

Metabolic engineering, which involves modifying the metabolic pathways within organisms to enhance the production of desired compounds or improve biochemical processes. Metabolic pathways are the series of chemical reactions that occur within a cell, governed by enzymes, to sustain life. By re-engineering these pathways, scientists can optimize the production of valuable substances such as biofuels, pharmaceuticals, and industrial chemicals. .

Metabolic engineering often starts with identifying and understanding the natural metabolic pathways of an organism. Scientists then modify these pathways by introducing new genes, removing existing ones, or altering the expression levels of certain enzymes to redirect the flow of metabolic intermediates towards the production of target compounds. .

For example, bacteria can be engineered to produce biofuels by introducing genes that enable the conversion of sugars into ethanol or other alcohols. Similarly, yeast can be modified to synthesize pharmaceuticals like insulin or artemisinin, a key anti-malarial drug. .

The benefits of metabolic engineering are significant, offering sustainable and cost-effective alternatives to traditional chemical synthesis methods. . By harnessing the natural capabilities of living organisms, metabolic engineering reduces the reliance on fossil fuels and minimizes environmental impact. Furthermore, it enables the production of complex molecules that are difficult or expensive to synthesize through conventional chemical processes. .

For example, the company Genzyme, a biotechnology company that specializes in developing innovative therapies for rare genetic disorders successfully engineered mammalian cells to produce recombinant human enzymes for enzyme replacement therapy. Patients with rare genetic disorders like Gaucher disease, who lack specific enzymes, can receive these engineered enzymes to break down harmful substances in their bodies. This approach not only improves the quality of life for patients but also demonstrates the potential of metabolic engineering to provide effective treatments for a range of genetic diseases.

Another compelling example of genetic circuits in biomedical engineering is their use in creating smart therapies for cancer treatment. Researchers have designed genetic circuits that can selectively target and kill cancer cells while sparing healthy cells. . One such circuit involves a synthetic gene network that detects cancer-specific markers and triggers the expression of a therapeutic gene, leading to the production of a protein that induces cell death in cancer cells. This precision targeting reduces the side effects commonly associated with conventional chemotherapy, offering a more effective and safer treatment option for cancer patients. .

CRISPR/Cas Systems

In recent years, CRISPR/Cas systems have revolutionized the field of genetic engineering and synthetic biology. CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) and its associated protein Cas (CRISPR-associated) provide a powerful and precise tool for editing the genomes of living organisms. This technology, originally discovered as part of a bacterial immune system, allows scientists to make targeted modifications to DNA sequences with unprecedented accuracy and efficiency. .

CRISPR/Cas systems work by using a guide RNA to direct the Cas protein to a specific location in the genome, where it makes a precise cut in the DNA. This cut can then be repaired by the cell's natural repair mechanisms, allowing for the insertion, deletion, or modification of genetic material. This precise control over genetic information enables a wide range of applications, from correcting genetic defects and improving crop resilience to engineering microbes for environmental cleanup and sustainable manufacturing. .

The impact of CRISPR/Cas technology extends beyond basic research. In medicine, it holds promise for treating genetic disorders by correcting mutations at their source. In agriculture, it enables the development of crops with enhanced traits, such as increased yield, disease resistance, and improved nutritional content. In industrial biotechnology, CRISPR/Cas facilitates the creation of microorganisms optimized for the production of biofuels, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals. .

In the development of gene therapies for genetic disorders, researchers have used CRISPR/Cas9 to correct mutations in genes responsible for conditions such as sickle cell anemia and muscular dystrophy. By precisely editing the defective genes in patients' cells, CRISPR/Cas9 has the potential to provide long-term cures for these debilitating diseases. In clinical trials, CRISPR-based therapies have shown promising results, bringing hope to patients and their families for effective and lasting treatments. .

2.1 Current Challenges in Designing and Predicting Synthetic Biological Systems

Synthetic biology is an exciting field where scientists design and build new biological systems or re-engineer existing ones to solve real-world problems. However, creating and predicting how these systems work comes with significant challenges. Thankfully, artificial intelligence (AI) holds promise in tackling these problems. .

One major challenge in synthetic biology is the complexity and unpredictability of biological systems. Unlike machines, living organisms consist of intricate networks of molecules that interact in many different ways. This complexity poses challenges in predicting how a newly designed biological system will behave. For instance, when scientists design genetic circuits to make bacteria produce a specific protein, the bacteria's natural processes can interfere in unexpected ways, leading to inconsistent results. .

Another problem is the lack of standardization in the parts used to build these systems. For example, a genetic part that works well in one type of cell might not work the same way in another. This inconsistency makes designing reliable biological systems more difficult. A synthetic circuit that successfully controls gene expression in *Escherichia coli* might fail in yeast due to differences in their cellular environments. This lack of predictability necessitates extensive testing and adjustment for each new application. .

Integrating synthetic parts into living organisms is also challenging. These parts need to work well with the organism's natural systems without causing problems. Sometimes, the new parts can stress the organism or interfere with its normal functions, leading to unexpected results. . For example, inserting a synthetic metabolic pathway into a microbe to produce biofuels might divert too many resources from the cell's growth and reproduction processes, reducing the overall efficiency and stability of the system. .

Additionally, there are ethical and safety concerns. Ensuring that synthetic organisms are safe for the environment and people is crucial. This means having good regulations and making sure the public understands and supports what scientists do. For example, the release of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) into the environment must be carefully controlled to prevent unintended ecological consequences. .

2.2 AI in Biological Systems

2.2.1 Historical Perspective

The application of AI in biology has evolved significantly over the past few decades. Initially, AI methods were used primarily for data analysis and pattern recognition in biological datasets. Early applications included the use of neural networks for protein structure prediction and gene expression analysis. . As computational power and algorithmic sophistication increased, AI began to play a more integral role in modeling complex biological systems and aiding in the design of synthetic biological constructs. . The types of AI algorithms used are listed below.

2.3 Integration of AI into Synthetic Biology: A Synergistic Revolution

Artificial intelligence (AI) with synthetic biology is changing the landscape of biomedical engineering, biotechnology, medicine, and environmental science. This powerful duo helps scientists design and predict the behavior of synthetic biological systems more accurately and efficiently. .

One of the main ways AI helps in designing synthetic biological systems is through predictive modeling. This means AI algorithms, especially machine learning models, can analyze data from previous experiments and predict how new genetic designs will work. . For example, when designing genetic circuits (which are like the biological equivalent of electronic circuits but with genes), AI can simulate different setups and figure out which ones are likely to work best. This saves a lot of time and effort because scientists don't have to rely as much on trial and error. .

A good example of AI's impact on synthetic biology is optimizing metabolic pathways in microorganisms. Metabolic pathways are the series of chemical reactions that occur inside cells to keep them alive. Scientists often try to tweak these pathways to get cells to produce useful substances, like medicines or biofuels. . However, this can be very complex. AI, particularly through a type of algorithm called evolutionary algorithms, can explore many different pathway designs to find the most efficient ones. For instance, researchers have used AI to aid yeast cells produce more artemisinin, a key drug for treating malaria. By predicting how different changes to the yeast's metabolic network will affect production, AI has helped create yeast strains that make the drug production more efficiently. .

Another important application of AI in synthetic biology is predictive modeling and simulation. Before actually building and testing a synthetic biological system in the laboratory, scientists are able to use AI to simulate its behaviour. . These simulations can predict how the system will behave under different conditions and help optimize the design before any real-world testing. For example, AI has been used to model how engineered bacteria, designed to break down environmental pollutants, will behave in different environments. This helps ensure the bacteria will be effective and safe before they're released into the environment. .

One successful case study is the development of CAR-T cell therapies for cancer treatment. CAR-T cells are modified immune cells designed to attack cancer cells. Creating these therapies involves designing synthetic receptors that can recognize cancer cells. AI has been very useful in optimizing these designs. Machine learning models can analyze data from existing CAR-T therapies and identify the most effective receptor designs, making the treatments more precise and effective. This has improved the success rates of CAR-T therapies in targeting specific types of cancer and has led to better outcomes for patients.

Another example is using AI to improve the production of biofuels from algae. Algae can be engineered to produce biofuels, but getting them to do this efficiently is challenging.

Researchers have used AI to study the metabolic pathways of algae and found genetic changes that boost biofuel production. By predicting the effects of these changes, AI aided in the development of algae strains that produce biofuels more efficiently, supporting the development of sustainable energy solutions. .

3.0 Methodology

3.1 AI Algorithms for Designing Synthetic Biological Systems

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in synthetic biology represents a cutting-edge intersection of technology and biological sciences, with particular relevance to biomedical engineering and healthcare. . AI algorithms provide powerful tools for designing and predicting the behavior of synthetic biological systems, offering new possibilities for medical treatments, diagnostics, and biomanufacturing. This section delves into the detailed use of machine learning algorithms, neural networks, and evolutionary algorithms in synthetic biology. .

3.1.1 Machine Learning Algorithms

Machine learning (ML) algorithms are extensively used in synthetic biology to design and predict the behavior of biological systems. They can process vast amounts of data to identify patterns and make accurate predictions. .

3.1.2 Supervised Learning

Supervised learning involves training models on labeled data, where the input-output relationships are known. This method includes techniques like regression and classification. .

Regression: Researchers have used regression models to predict the expression levels of proteins in genetic circuits. For instance, by analyzing data from past experiments, ML models can forecast how changes in genetic components, like promoters or ribosome binding sites, will impact protein production in bacteria. This helps in designing more efficient biological systems with predictable outcomes. .

Classification: Classification algorithms categorize biological data. For example, they can distinguish between different cell types based on gene expression profiles, which is crucial for developing targeted therapies. In cancer research, classification models help in identifying cancerous cells from healthy ones, enabling more precise diagnostics and personalized treatments. .

3.1.3 Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised learning finds patterns in data without predefined labels, including clustering and dimensionality reduction. .

Clustering: Clustering algorithms group similar data points, which can identify new biological pathways or functions. For example, clustering gene expression data can reveal unknown regulatory networks within cells, providing insights into cellular processes and potential therapeutic targets. .

Dimensionality Reduction: Techniques like principal component analysis (PCA) simplify complex biological data by reducing the number of variables while retaining essential information. This is particularly useful in high-throughput experiments, such as genome sequencing, where it helps in visualizing and interpreting the data more efficiently. .

3.1.4 Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) involves training algorithms to make decisions by rewarding desired outcomes. In synthetic biology, RL optimizes experimental conditions and protocols.

For instance, RL algorithms can iteratively test different conditions for growing engineered microbes, learning over time which conditions produce the highest yields of a desired product, such as insulin or antibiotics. This approach minimizes trial-and-error and accelerates the development of efficient biomanufacturing processes. .

3.1.5 Neural Networks

Neural networks, particularly deep learning models, are powerful tools for modeling complex biological systems. They can capture non-linear relationships and interactions within biological data, making them ideal for tasks like gene expression prediction and protein folding. .

3.1.6 Deep Learning Architectures

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs): CNNs analyze spatial data, such as images. In synthetic biology, CNNs can analyze microscopy images to identify cellular structures or detect anomalies in tissue samples, aiding in disease diagnosis and monitoring. .

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs): RNNs handle sequential data, making them useful for modeling genetic sequences. They can predict the effects of mutations in DNA sequences, helping design genes with desired characteristics or understanding the genetic basis of diseases.

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs): GANs generate synthetic data. In synthetic biology, GANs can create realistic biological data, such as synthetic gene expression profiles, which can train other ML models or simulate biological experiments. This is particularly useful when experimental data is scarce or expensive to obtain.

3.1.7 Evolutionary Algorithms

Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) mimic natural selection to optimize solutions. They are particularly useful in synthetic biology for optimizing genetic constructs and metabolic pathways.

Genetic Algorithms (GAs): GAs use processes similar to biological evolution, such as selection, crossover, and mutation, to evolve solutions to optimization problems. In synthetic biology, GAs optimize genetic circuits by iteratively improving designs to achieve desired behaviours, such as higher protein production or more efficient metabolic pathways.

Evolutionary Strategies: Evolutionary strategies optimize continuous variables and are used to fine-tune parameters in biological systems. For example, they can optimize the concentration of different substrates in a bioreactor to maximize the yield of a bioproduct, such as biofuels or pharmaceuticals.

3.2 Predicting Behaviour of Synthetic Biological Systems

Predicting the behaviour of synthetic biological systems is a crucial aspect of synthetic biology, enabling scientists to design efficient and reliable biological constructs. AI algorithms, dynamic modeling techniques, and simulation tools play significant roles in this process. This

section explores the techniques for predictive modeling, the software tools used for simulations, and real-world case studies that illustrate the practical applications and outcomes of these predictive approaches. .

3.2.1 Dynamic Modeling of Genetic Circuits

Dynamic modeling involves creating mathematical representations of genetic circuits to predict their behaviour over time. These models simulate how genes, proteins, and other components interact within a cell, providing insights into the system's dynamics under various conditions. .

For example, researchers have used dynamic modeling to design synthetic oscillators—genetic circuits that produce rhythmic outputs, similar to biological clocks. By modeling the interactions between different genetic components, scientists can predict how changes in promoter strength or protein degradation rates will affect the circuit's oscillatory behaviour. This allows for the fine-tuning of genetic circuits to achieve desired temporal patterns. .

3.2.2 Predictive Analytics for Metabolic Pathways

Predictive analytics involves using statistical models and machine learning algorithms to forecast the outcomes of modifying metabolic pathways. This approach helps in optimizing the production of desired compounds by engineered microorganisms. `.

In one notable case, researchers used predictive analytics to enhance the production of isobutanol, a biofuel, in *E. coli*. By analyzing large datasets from previous experiments, machine learning models identified key genetic modifications that significantly increased isobutanol yield. This predictive approach enabled the efficient design of high-yielding bacterial strains, thereby reducing the need for extensive experimental trials. .

3.2.3 Software and Tools for Simulating Synthetic Biological Systems

Several software tools are widely used for simulating synthetic biological systems, each offering unique features for modeling, analysis, and optimization. .

MATLAB, a high-level programming environment, combined with the SimBiology toolbox, provides comprehensive tools for modeling and simulating biological systems. SimBiology allows for the construction of detailed mechanistic models of genetic circuits and metabolic pathways, enabling the simulation of complex biological processes. .

COBRA (Constraint-Based Reconstruction and Analysis) is a framework for modeling metabolic networks using constraint-based approaches. It allows researchers to simulate the flow of metabolites through a network, predicting the effects of genetic modifications on metabolic fluxes. COBRA has been used extensively to optimize microbial strains for biofuel production and other biotechnological applications. .

3.2.4 AI-Based Simulation Approaches

AI-based simulation approaches integrate machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques with traditional modeling tools to enhance predictive accuracy and computational efficiency. .

For instance, deep learning models have been used to predict the folding of proteins, a complex process that determines protein function. By training neural networks on large datasets of protein structures, researchers can predict the three-dimensional folding of new proteins with high accuracy. This capability is crucial for designing synthetic proteins with specific functions in therapeutic and industrial applications. .

4.0 Case Studies

4.1 Case Study 1: Dynamic Modeling of Synthetic Oscillators

In a study aimed at designing synthetic genetic oscillators, researchers used dynamic modeling to predict the behaviour of different genetic circuit configurations. By simulating various promoter strengths and feedback loops, the models accurately predicted which configurations would produce stable oscillations. This guided the experimental design, leading to the successful construction of synthetic oscillators in *E. coli*. The oscillators showed consistent rhythmic behaviour, demonstrating the power of predictive modeling in synthetic biology. .

4.2 Case Study 2: Predictive Analytics for Isobutanol Production

A significant application of predictive analytics was demonstrated in optimizing *E. coli* for isobutanol production. Machine learning models analyzed data from numerous genetic

modifications and identified key changes that enhanced biofuel production. The predictions were validated experimentally, resulting in engineered strains with substantially higher isobutanol yields. This case highlights how predictive analytics can streamline metabolic engineering processes, making biofuel production more efficient and cost-effective. .

4.3 Case Study 3: AI-Based Simulation of Protein Folding

Researchers at DeepMind developed AlphaFold, an AI-based simulation tool for predicting protein folding. By leveraging deep learning techniques, AlphaFold accurately predicted the structures of a wide range of proteins, surpassing traditional methods. This breakthrough has significant implications for drug discovery and the design of synthetic proteins. The ability to predict protein structures with high accuracy accelerates the development of new therapies and industrial enzymes, showcasing the transformative potential of AI in synthetic biology. .

5.0 Discussion.

These case studies underscore several important lessons:

5.1 Integration of AI into Traditional Methods

Combining AI with traditional modeling approaches enhances predictive accuracy and efficiency. AI models can process large datasets and identify patterns that are not apparent through conventional methods alone. .

5.2 Validation Through Experimentation

Predictive models must be validated through experimental data. While models can provide valuable insights, experimental validation ensures that the predictions hold true in real-world conditions. .

5.3 Iterative Optimization

Predictive modeling and simulation are iterative processes. Continuous refinement of models based on new data and experimental feedback leads to progressively more accurate predictions and optimized designs. .

5.4 Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Successful applications of AI in synthetic biology often involve interdisciplinary collaboration between biologists, engineers, and data scientists. This collaborative approach leverages diverse expertise to tackle complex biological challenges. .

6.0 Conclusion

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into synthetic biology represents a groundbreaking synergy that is revolutionizing the field. This paper explored the dual roles of AI in designing and predicting the behaviour of synthetic biological systems, highlighting the transformative potential of AI-driven methodologies. The challenges inherent in synthetic biology—such as the complexity and variability of biological systems, the lack of standardization in genetic components, and the integration of synthetic parts into living organisms—underscore the need for advanced computational tools. AI algorithms, including machine learning, neural networks, evolutionary algorithms, and reinforcement learning, provide powerful solutions to these challenges by enabling more accurate, efficient, and predictive designs. .

The application of dynamic modeling and predictive analytics, as illustrated through various case studies, demonstrates the practical impact of AI in synthetic biology. From optimizing genetic circuits and metabolic pathways to pioneering AI-based simulations of protein folding, these advancements underpin the efficiency of AI in enhancing the predictability and functionality of synthetic biological systems. Successful real-world applications, such as the development of CAR-T cell therapies and the optimization of biofuel production, further validate the utility of AI-driven approaches. .

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